

MEN AND WOMEN SPEECH PECULARITIES AND EXCEPTIONS

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Abstract. This article examines and discusses gender differences in language using the author's recorded conversations. The dissertation will begin with a detailed explanation of the research context in this area. He then proceeds to analyze the data, looking at the comparisons that can be made between the study here and previous studies in the field. It will also include a discussion of relevant issues arising from the analysis of this research.

Key words: gender role, speech, conversation, intervention, comparison process.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ И ИСКЛЮЧЕНИЯ РЕЧИ МУЖЧИН И ЖЕНЩИН

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются и обсуждаются гендерные различия в языке с использованием записей разговоров автора. Диссертация начнется с подробного объяснения контекста исследований в этой области. Затем он приступает к анализу данных, рассматривая сравнения, которые можно провести между данным исследованием и предыдущими исследованиями в этой области. Он также будет включать обсуждение актуальных вопросов, возникающих в результате анализа данного исследования.

Ключевые слова: гендерная роль, речь, беседа, вмешательство, процесс сравнения.

Introduction

For the study of gender and speech, conversations are recorded so that they can be translated and analyzed to provide data for discussing these issues. A key difference in the language of women and men is that men have shown to dominate conversation through the use of pauses and overlaps, and that the number of these irregularities of conversation increases significantly when men speak. There is clearly a difference in the amount of interventions men and women use, with men being more likely to intervene and less likely to do so. Considering the size of the study and the way in which one participant differs significantly from the other, it cannot be said that this is due to gender differences, and it was interfered with the fact that the participants differed only from each other, not men, reluctance to participate. The female part interrupts men, and men pick up women more often than men.

Research methodology

The traditional view of differences between men and women is the use of offensive words and ugly language. This is explained by the prevalence of expressions such as "feminine" behavior or "a gentleman's curse", which indicates the belief that cursing is a purely masculine habit. Many claims have been made about the speaking styles of women and men in this field. Jespersen argues that women are inherently flawed in their vulgar and vulgar expressions and prefer to express themselves secretly and indirectly. (in some areas) Flexner states that "more American dialects are made and used by men".

Discussion

Lakoff also argued that while men call each other names more loudly, women use more polite language such as "shit" and "oh god". Lakoff highlighted the use of the "question mark" as

an illustration of this. It states that women use more marked questions than men. Fewer answers to these questions will give you more confidence. Recent studies have shown that tag issues are more often associated with female language (Siegler and Siegler), which illustrates people's attitudes towards women and their insecurity.

However, the study for this test found very different results, with men using the labels more often than women. Interestingly, none of the problems classified, which were considered more common due to excessive use of pauses, were addressed. Perhaps this is important because the more aggressive speech style used can also make it more confident in its speech. However, it cannot be said to be gender related as he uses mostly group-tagged questions.

Another form of language that has been identified as questionable speech is the use of closures, such as gender, type, etc. Lakoff described them as an element of female language that makes their language less direct. In this study, it was found that the women who participated actually used fences more often than men.

Results

This study seeks to explore differences between women's and men's language. And although the overall picture from a small study group cannot be summarized, it indicates that speech patterns vary greatly in some areas. Determining whether it is similar or just a difference in speech style requires further research. But in this group: the two men were the most interrupted and the two women the most interrupted; a woman used the most active hearing aids and a man the least; a man spoke more and a woman spoke less; both women used different obstacles, which meant dubious speech; and the two men used more vulgar terms.

Conclusion

These basic facts show that there are and can be many factors influencing this investigation, such as nationality, length of relationship, length of tenure with the company, and at least the fact that the investigator is male. It seems that some research results from twenty to twenty years ago are still valid today. These results are remarkable considering how each actor grew up in a very different society twenty or thirty years ago. The concepts of gender equality and women's rights are not new, and the responses of the participants in this study demonstrate awareness and commitment to equality.

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